

**IMPACT ON PROJECT COST MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN
INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES DOER FACTORS**

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Annotation: This article describes the factors affecting the effective management of project costs in industrial enterprises. The results of research conducted by local and foreign scientists on effective use of project costs are described. Scientific and practical suggestions are given on ways to effectively manage project costs in industrial enterprises.

Keywords: project, cost, estimate, efficiency, factors, economic activity, variable cost, fixed cost.

INTRODUCTION. Project costs in industrial enterprises have a complex structure therefore, following the process of ensuring the effectiveness of their managementrow factors effect does:

- organizational mechanism;
- manage methods;
- personnel qualification;
- material - technical base;
- of the country economic policy;
- in the market competitive environment;
- information supply.

Project costs manage process one how many stages own into received because of his sequence, own in time done increase to the organizational mechanism of management depends.

In practice expenses features, formation place and time, their role in economic activity, the need for accuracy in calculation attention taken, manager by management

methods right to choose is necessary.

Management decisions acceptance from doing pulling until economy of activity to the end, ie intended to the goal until you reach has been in process personnel of the factor mental and professional qualification expenses manage efficiency in providing participation is enough.

As the efficiency of project costs in industrial enterprises is also provided by labor productivity, labor productivity is important for industrial enterprises. modernization level connection being how much it is important that it is provided with innovative techniques and technologies is considered.

In the country tax of politics optimal organize to be done industrial enterprises excess tax from the load free will do since the size of the profit increasing economy conduct of activity duration too providing gives

The above-mentioned factors affect the activity of industrial enterprises positive effect to show information of supply how much good to the road to be placed a lot in terms of connection reliable, own in time and necessary it is unreasonable to move without information. Management in this methods and mechanism management efficiency in providing external and internal environment about information of supply efficiency separately place occupies.

In the conditions of economic modernization, increasing the effective management of project costs in industrial enterprises is timely from external information source to be able to use, implement the happening news in a timely manner is provided by doing. To this end, to modernize the economy to the conditions information on adaptation of industrial enterprises. It also depends on the armament of its supply to meet the requirements of the time. The reason is that modern information systems reduce the volume of work, a way to lighten work, speed up work, waste excess paper not to put management to the process innovative new ideas enters.

METHODS. Project management in the activity information of supply importance regarding the first President I. Karimov so thoughts we bring can: "Today in the day our lives computer tin information technologies, internet, mobile telephone

unrelated imagination by doing will not be" [1].

Ye.L. Shuremov, D.V.Chistov, G.V.Lyamov's in textbooks "Business of management modern efficient method enterprise economy all information of its activity affecting the conduct and organization of business collection and analysis to do demand does" [2] that enterprise management in the activity information of supply importance open to give movement done.

Russian scientists S.V.Amelin and of the competitions scientific In the works, "information supply process incurs costs, them manage processes purpose and functionalization directions descriptive economic data and processes actions complex [3] cited that.

X.S.Zaynutdinov and SH.N.Zaynutdinovlar own in the textbook "The main goal of the communication process is the head of the organization and the arm necessary for a certain level of relationship between subordinates was treatment tool calculated of information be understood consists of providing" [4], [5], in the management process of information supply importance explained.

T.P.Jiyemuratov in his studies "...optimal information supply is not only enterprise achieve successes and his It is a guarantee of competitiveness, but sometimes it is a strict competition in his own circumstances activities save a means of staying participation as well enough," thought that stated.

B.A.Begalov in his work to create an informed society the concept of formation of the information and communication market, econometric modeling methods and them development trends offer reached [6].

M.N.Kambarov own in his studies information and communication technologies activities efficient organize reach and A comprehensive and systematic study of the management process of development is effective from them use methods offer reached [7].

Expenses manage efficiency increase information supply. A lot of rational organization in terms of depends, in this mainly information right classification, information of sources reliability, speed, information to the base have to be with is

expressed.

There are two types of information supply, accounted and unaccounted for can be studied separately. Information is taken into account sources accounting, tax and operative reports, account unobtainable sources internal and external check, auditor conclusions, tax office check the results input possible

Management account expenses manage instrument as shareholding of society common strategic development based on expenses about information collection and to communicate of input better methods aim to provide does.

Work release expenses about information system of formation necessity the first go XX of the century in their heads G. Emerson "Work productivity, work right and of work operativeness basis as" named in the book statement made [8]. In it first times of the report work release expenses account independent direction to separate as movement done

Disclosure of the content of the management account and the use of information giver different different concepts economic available in the literature.

SSSatubaldina's according to "management account expenses classification, cost formation by product types, profit center, budgeting, reports on costs and their analysis with work take to go activity type" [9] explained that.

V.B.Ivashkevich stated "management account enterprise in the activity all of expenses analysis, account and integrates planning into one system" [10] to replace the information explained.

So, management in the account information structure from him users requirements depends without is formed. His in the base work release account information there is being this managers to make operational decisions in the field of production necessary information is considered.

RESULTS. Management account expenses in management main content is that she is present did data using expenses analysis together with the adoption of decisions, it has the following tasksto the front puts:

- expenses surface coming registration in place and by species;

- expenses classification;
- sold out product and activity type according to expenses assessment;
- the price management;
- expenses analysis, their content, dynamics study;
- preparation of information in making management decisions.

Documentation, control, assessment, calculation of management accounting, in accounts reflection carry on analysis and forecasting, accountability, information such as instruments expenses as a basis for making tactical and strategic management decisions service does.

Market of the economy dynamic conditions economic information with at work his efficiency increase for information as follows classification can:

- direction according to (internal and external);
- repetition according to (current and emergency);
- object according to (enterprise, department, product);
- time according to (known term in, to the date).

Expenses in all periods of activity of joint-stock companies. There is a problem of management, which in turn is the momentum of the economy changes with depends. Shareholding societies such in the circumstances own activities in equilibrium holding standing and high economic to the degree to achieve the micro and macro economic conditions of the economy taking into account the quick and efficient use of available resources increase necessary.

The information system of joint-stock companies meets the following requirements to give need:

- to all forms of ownership of joint-stock companies flexible to be;
- economic, financial and has the volume of indicators used in production activities to be;
- integrity, that is, the intended functions of all information systems his system under purposeful functions with adaptations means;

- modularity, the only one of the base complete integrated during of the system separately from departments autonomous use and operative management clear issues limitation;

- of the system functional and structural in terms of perfection, network release, economic functions cover take.

The economy modernization conditions shareholding societies expenses efficient manage for management activity own into of the organization in addition to the goals and objectives of cost management related to the implementation of all commercial and business plans the system formation a must.

Expenses manage system efficient activity many to factors depends. Most main of the factors one of managers technical, personal, financial systems in line information resources with right to work organize get ability is considered.

Management of information resources in the process of effective management of project costs in industrial enterprises to the following depends to be can:

- activities of industrial enterprises all project costs during periods manage problem there is being this own in turn associated with rapid changes in the economy. Industrial enterprises are like that in the circumstances own activities in equilibrium holding standing and high economic to the degree reach for economy of keeping micro and taking into account the macroeconomic conditions, using the available resources quickly and fruitful to use done to increase necessary;

- future, current and operational planning of project costs decisions optimization and again work;

- project costs efficient manage indicators system formation;

- regulatory, plan and actual costs of the project indicators identify;

- all stages of the production process and management levels indicators analysis.

Above counting passed actions expenses can be considered as a holistic process of information provision in management. Operational and effective project cost

management depends on the optimal organization of enterprise information supply.

Information technologies effective implementation is ensured only in conditions where managers clearly understand their capabilities. It also depends on their collection, registration, delivery, processing, storage, presentation and preparation of information, analysis and management decisions.

Information here is used to make management decisions necessary information a set of resources with is expressed.

Information technologies information in the system information collect, storage, again work and transmission methods to determine means. Information in the system information again of work technological process technical and software tools own into received separately from operations consists, moreover, of effective functionalization of cost management for complex automation, ie of the enterprise all departments is supported by working together. The organizational unit of management consists of a managing person and an organizational structure that performs management functions using information technology tools of the information system.

Functional components form the basis of the information system, that is, models and algorithms that receive management information.

Functional structure – management system functions done increasing functional subsystem systems, ie information again work is a complex.

Effective project cost management system main characteristics one his dynamic, ie enterprise to the front placed tasks to the description depends internal and external in the environment change surface coming with information to the system demand too will change.

DISCUSSION. So making the project costs manage system efficient functionalization for information system the following tools with provide required:

- efficient documentation provide;
- modern software tools to build and to use;
- necessary technical supply organize to do.

All the tools listed above are necessary, that is, long and short in deadlines issues to solve help giving information complex to create take will come Efficient information supply expenses manage necessary for the system is a tool.

It is known from practice that it has a complex production system enterprises project costs and financial the results optimization, operative to make informed management decisions economic to information big need they feel of information lack of and of quality low enterprise project costs efficient manage opportunities significant level reduces. Current in the circumstances this significant to losses, work issued of the product of competitiveness decrease, in sales to interruptions and that's it such as row negative to unpleasantness can bring.

Project costs of industrial enterprises manage system in the composition expenses about sure and operative information who prepares information supply system separate to put appropriate because this economy of activity results status about information to users deliver the only one system is considered.

Economist scientist A.SH. Gudaybergenov [11] for information economic resource as definition giving "1S-enterprise" automated emphasized the advantages of using the communication system in enterprise management. This system is of great importance in the formation of the information base of the enterprise, but at the same time it was considered appropriate to simplify the method of its use. ERP system is one of the modern ways of managing production resources, based on the use of modern computer technologies.

ERP - (Enterprise Resource Planning - management of enterprise resources) is work release and service show a method of effective planning and management of all resources of the enterprise necessary for the implementation of sales, production, purchase and calculation according to customer orders. The information system operating within this method is called the ERP class system.

ERP – all major business operations within the scope of the enterprise planning, count, control to do and analysis to do automation for the only one the system to form possibility giving integrated suggestions complex in itself summing up is a system.

They are from among work release resources planning, work we can distinguish operational management, calculation and analysis of activity results over the output plan.

CONCLUSION. The goal of the ERP method is to gain an advantage over competitors and to develop a more effective tool for product cost management optimization of all activities of the enterprise. Achieving this goal for ERP – class in the system work release of the process the following directions to improve possibility giving manage and planning separately methods work exit to the goal compatible with:

- business production of products in the shortest possible time and at the lowest cost with the help of process optimization;
- strengthening the implementation of control over supply and demand by shortening the production cycle;
- in the process of receiving orders, their implementation enable formation for enterprise power evaluation.

So, conclusion to do it is possible that the use of the ERP-class system will provide a significant opportunity for the enterprise in front of its competitors due to a significant reduction of project costs and optimization of business processes .

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